

TEACHING ENGLISH LITERATURE ONLINE IN UZBEKISTAN

¹Rakhimova Kh. K., ²Matrasulova Maftuna Matyakubovna

¹Senior lecturer, Foreign Philology faculty, Urgench State University

²Bachelor's student, Foreign Philology faculty, Urgench State University

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Abstract. *The teaching process in Uzbekistan changed unexpectedly due to the Covid-19. Educational system turned into online. This sudden shift arose several difficulties for both teachers and for students. Teachers started to prepare the teaching materials in Moodle platform, they had uploaded thousands of important documents and materials related to every subject. Students came across with internet connection problems. Moreover, most of the students faced difficulties with studying online because they were adapted for traditional way of teaching and learning. In this article the process of studying online, the obstacles and advantages of studying online are discussed*

Keywords: *teaching literature, online lessons, distance learning, students.*

Introduction

Teaching online was not very common till the pandemic time. In our country online teaching became very popular in 2020. At that time teachers and learners had to quickly adapt to a new environment, because traditional way of teaching immediately turned into online teaching and learning. Teachers worked on preparing resource for teaching students. The process was very difficult due to the fact that it was great responsibility to organize a new style of teaching very efficiently.

Students at first could not adapt to a new teaching process because of internet connection problems, moreover, they were adapted to the traditional fact to face lessons, so that even for most of the students it was hard to understand the lessons and participate during the lessons. However, the beginning of the online teaching was not so successful, with the help of teacher's diligence the process become more and more useful and easy. Students started to accept this type of education. Furthermore, appearing challenges in terms of teaching and learning started to reduce. Finally, the online environment became the reality in teaching and learning process. No matter what kind of obstacles are faced the educators and learners tried and even these days are trying to adapt to study online.

Literature review

Before it has been pointed that online teaching process should be simple and friendly. Moreover, pedagogical principles of designing a lesson should be similar with traditional face-to-face teaching environment. (Lie & Cano, 2001).

The materials related to literature and linguistics that are taught in online environment were more difficult in EFL teaching. (Hassan, 2018). Though students can face difficulties if they lack language skills. In addition, it can lead to reduce interests of students in terms of reading and learning literature. (Hassan, 2018; Mohammed, 2017). To help students while learning literature teachers should use different types of approaches. In that case students will not face problems with lack of language. (Mohammed, 2017).

Main body

Literature lesson can improve students' language use both orally and in context. Depending on organized by teachers' materials at literature lessons they can at the same time improve their skills like: reading, writing, speaking, listening and vocabulary. As in our modern world technology and multimedia is really developed, for teaching students at University it was used Moodle platform. It is a very popular and free platforms that gives chance to teachers to create their websites with dynamic courses. So that reason this platform was chosen in our country also to teach students. Via this platform's students gained knowledge how to do different tasks and also, they became more proficient in terms of using such kind of platforms, and dealing with any kind of online based tasks. Moreover, Zoom application was used in order to organize real class atmosphere. With the help of this application teachers could manage a lot of things like:

- Checking the presence;
- Participation during the lessons;
- Organizing questionnaires;
- Showing before prepared videos related to the theme;
- Evaluating students according to their activeness;
- Using gamifications and other different methods.

The main difficulties were connected with Internet connection. Challenges that teachers face during the online lesson was to control the presence of every student, because most of the students could not participate in online lectures because of poor internet connection and with electricity problems. Moreover, there were students who were online but actually there were not listening the lectures, again connected with somehow not stable connection.

Teachers were trying hard to provide and teach their students with enough materials and tests for practicing. Most of the students understanding this hard work, were doing the tasks on time with responsibility.

Another problem is that not every student could swallow the online materials and do the tasks efficiently as they were used to study traditionally. But after experiencing it in reality they started to adapt to the process of learning.

Furthermore, the best challenge for students was the assessment in the process of online studying. Owing to the fact that tests were uploaded to the Moodle platform with exact time and in final exams there was only one attempt for doing the test. It means that if while doing the test you face connection problems, you can fail the exam or get low marks, no matter how well you know the subject actually. Before starting the test, students should take into consideration the time and problems with internet connection. Most of the students can be demotivated after getting low marks, and their interest in terms of subject can be lost. Unfortunately, teachers could not help with such kind of occasions, because before the exam they organize everything automatically, teachers take into account every problem that can students face.

Advantages of online teaching is that, students learned not only themes of the literature lessons, but at the same time they improved their knowledge in the sphere of technology and multimedia. If in the future they will face such kind of situations that occurred in pandemic period as in our country, they will be ready to cope with every challenge because they have experienced teaching and learning online.

Methods that used during the teaching literature online

Student-centered approach in this approach students mostly participate and teacher is a person who just gives instructions and show how to deal with activities and tasks. Students may

work in small groups or it can be pair work, teacher can divide and give task to work together, mostly project works can be given, in order to improve learner's creativity, critical thinking, problem solving skills, teacher gives appropriate tasks according to curriculum. This approach also offers greater flexibility for working with small groups or with pair. Moreover, students feel themselves more motivated and they learn how to set goals and how to achieve them. Another thing that should be said that, in this approach students feel great responsibility while doing tasks.

The disadvantage of this approach that teacher's power and responsibility reduce during the lessons. Another disadvantage that teachers spend great deal of time for checking the assignments of students and assessment is a bit complicated. (Renton prep)

Visual method is used while teaching lessons via the Zoom, at literature lessons teachers used different types of Photos, Videos, Diagrams, Tables and other visual materials related to the theme. While giving information about famous writers and poets, teacher shows the photo and learners memorize that person. Moreover, teacher uses videos to initiate with autobiography of a writers and poets. As in one class there could be found visual learners it would be useful for them to memorize and study the materials easily.

Game-based teaching. In this type of teaching it is easy to attract student's attention, because the techniques are used in this approach will be interesting for almost every student. They are eager to participate in different kind of fun activities rather than just sitting and listening the boring lectures related to lecture. Makes the lesson more interesting depends on teacher so teacher should know how to use this approach appropriately while teaching. Teacher is a controller and organizer and making it useful and fun depends on student's active participation.

The one disadvantage in using gamification is that, students get used to study topics through games and activities, and whenever teacher is not going to organize activities and games on several lessons, students start to ask organizing them, it means that if teacher does not organize activities, students do not want to participate during the lessons and they easily get bored.

Project-based learning. As the name suggest it is a type of learning when students' complete projects. While teaching online teacher gives on task to the students and it will be their project work, teacher explains the standards of completing the project and students can work whether in small groups, whether in pairs and complete the project. In this approach learner again will be in the center of lesson. What is beneficial with this, that students' creativity grows, improves speaking ability, self-confidence also increases because being at the center of the class takes responsibility and students start to believe their knowledge after getting positive feedback and reward from their teachers.

In project-based learning there is one drawback that not every student can cope with doing projects, as in one class there are multi-level students it can be hard for most of the students to do the tasks given by teachers. That is why while teaching multi-level students' teacher should take into account the level of their students as well. Otherwise teacher and students can face misunderstandings while the process of assessment.

Communicative approach is also used in online environment while teaching literature lessons via Zoom, using this approach during the lessons helps students to improve their both language skills and general knowledge. While discussing the literature questions students use their target language and also at the same time they get information about the literature topics.

In this approach learners get stage and mostly answer the questions of teachers, participated in activities organized by teacher, prepare speech related to tasks, and feels responsibility in each lesson. Teacher is here checker of thoughts and ideas and evaluator of the active participation.

Conclusion

However, teaching online process was not very satisfactory at first, day by day teachers and learners started to adjust to the online environment. They started to understand that online learning also has its advantages. The students felt that they can use their time efficiently and also they were saving their time, because there was no need for going educational places and spend much time on way, but just sitting at home there were gaining the knowledge that was important for them.

The reaserchers from other countries suggested to integrate face-to-face and online learning as a way of supplementing process. The Navigation Social Worlds toolbox sustains chances for both online and offline settings. For instance, it includes materials related to reading, and students can learn anywhere and any time they want. There are variety of quizzes for getting quick feedback as well. (Dumitrica & Jarmula, 2022; Lim, Dannels, & Watkins, 2008), (Lie & Cano, 2001).

Due to the Covid-19 the education system in Uzbeksitan experienced teaching and learning online. Nowadays both teachers and learners without any problems can continue online studying because, they have experience and data for teaching and learning online. Today the online environment would not be problematic as it was before. Thanks to teachers' hard work students gained a lot of information related to sujetcs and they gained knowledge in terms of using technology and multimedia platforms, that makes their learning process easy.

In addition, teaching and learning literature lessons online also experienced by the side of learners, as a result student's interests in terms of the subject really increased. As nowadays students eager to use technological devices, it was interesting for them learning literature lessons via applications and multimedia platforms. Today students have valuable knowledge in terms of literature, that they have gained while studying online.

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